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High rates of marine organic carbon burial on the southwest Greenland margin induced by Neoglacial advances

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Marine sediments in glacially-carved fjords at high latitudes feature high organic carbon (OC) burial rates, but there are fewer data on the role of glacial activity on high-latitude OC burial rates outside of fjords. Here, we investigate the relationship between sediment OC burial rates in the deep troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf and Holocene glacial dynamics. Since the onset of prominent Neoglacial advances ~2500 years ago, the nature of the OC buried in the deep troughs and basins of the shelf was influenced by the glacier-driven increase in sediment accumulation rates (SAR), reactive iron (oxyhydr)oxide concentrations and fine-grain sediment, while OC burial rates were primarily enhanced by increasing SAR. Peak OC burial rates ($\sim 18.5 \pm 5.7 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$) in the deep troughs and basins of the shelf during the past ~1300 years are comparable to those of many high-latitude fjords, and the inferred total annual OC burial in these trough and basin areas is equivalent to ~5% of the annual CO₂ uptake by the Labrador Sea deep convection.

Burial of carbon in marine environments exerts a critical role on the global carbon cycle, as organic carbon (OC) burial in sediments serves as one of the most important net sinks for atmospheric CO₂^{1–3}. This is especially true for Arctic and subarctic environments where chemical weathering rates of silicate rocks are in part impeded by cold temperatures and a lack of liquid water^{4,5}. At high latitudes, high rates of OC burial, including OC of terrestrial and marine origin, in marine sediments have been documented in fjords that are long, deep and narrow estuaries formed during glacial periods^{6,7}. On the other hand, it has been reported that warming-induced glacier retreat can mobilize terrestrial OC, leading to enhanced terrestrial OC burial in Arctic marine sediments⁸. However, direct records of OC burial in marine sediments in response to episodic or long-term glacial activity, i.e., glacier advance and retreat, outside of fjords at high latitudes are not available.

The present interglacial, the Holocene (last 11,700 years), has been characterized by an overall warm climate, but millennial-scale changes in atmospheric temperature have occurred during this period, notably at high latitudes of the Northern Hemisphere⁹. The Early Holocene rapid warming and Late Holocene cooling events are noteworthy as distinct climate intervals in the northern North Atlantic region^{10,11}, although they lack global synchronization¹². Both the Early and Late Holocene intervals are accompanied by varying glacial conditions in Greenland, with major features

including, respectively, a glacier retreat after the last glacial period and the Neoglacial cooling of the recent millennia¹³.

Changes in glacial conditions are normally accompanied by variations in the rates and patterns of glacial erosion and meltwater discharge, which can supply large quantities of OC carrier phases such as fine-grained minerals, e.g., clays, fine silts, reactive iron (defined as the sum of Fe-oxides and Fe-oxyhydroxides; hereafter FeO_x)^{14–16}, and contribute nutrients that promote autochthonous OC production^{17–19}. Furthermore, glacial activity also impacts sediment accumulation rates (SAR)²⁰ that can modulate the dissolved oxygen penetration depth in sediments²¹ and, in turn, alter OC oxygen exposure time and thus influence oxidative degradation rates^{22,23}. Therefore, the variable Holocene glacial conditions and the resultant ice dynamics of marine-terminating glaciers over Greenland would have potentially caused fluctuations in sedimentary OC burial rates on the Greenland shelf. Notably, the Greenland shelf generally consists of shallower (a few hundred meters water depth) regions where most Holocene and present-day sediments have been swept away by strong bottom currents, and deeper troughs and basins (>~300 m water depth)^{24,25} where sediment deposition has occurred during the Holocene.

The southwest Greenland shelf witnessed distinct changes in Greenland glacial conditions (advance or retreat) during the Holocene, and its

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deeper troughs and basins hosted sediment deposits originating from the Greenland continent that were modulated by glacial dynamics²⁶, but the shelf experienced limited variations in sea-ice cover, another environmental factor that can alter sea-surface OC production^{13,27}. Marine sediments from this margin should thus provide a record of the relationship between southwest Greenland glacial activity and OC burial rates unaffected by significant changes in sea-ice conditions.

To investigate this relationship, we analyzed a marine sediment core (SA13-ST3-20G; water depth 498 m) recovered from a deep basin of the southwest Greenland shelf, offshore Nuuk in the northeast Labrador Sea (Fig. 1). Principal component analyses, PCA1 scores, based on X-ray fluorescence data obtained on three proglacial threshold lakes (Lake IS21, Badesø and Langesø) in the Kobbefjord area of southwest Greenland²⁸ (Figs. 1 and 2a) were used to represent the southwest Greenland glacial activity during the Holocene. The PCA1 scores above 0 indicate a glacier advance²⁸. This analysis indicates that an overall persistent glacier advance occurred since ~2.5 cal. ka BP (thousands of calibrated years BP), although the reconstructed glacial activity pattern shows asynchronous features (Fig. 2a) due to local temperature differences²⁸. This timing is largely coincident with the recent findings that Greenland glaciers expanded during three distinct periods of ~2.5–1.7 cal. ka BP, ~1.3–1.0 cal. ka BP and ~0.7–0.1 cal. ka BP²⁹ (Fig. 2).

In addition to autochthonous OC production in the surface waters and/or allochthonous OC supply from marine and/or terrestrial environments, the accumulation and preservation of OC at the seafloor are strongly influenced by catabolic processes (microbial biodegradation and remineralization). OC accumulation and preservation can be enhanced by binding and adsorption onto the surface of fine-grained mineral particles, and can also be promoted by rapid sedimentation. In this context, we present integrated geochemical data, including total OC and nitrogen (N) concentrations (TOC and TN), metal elemental concentrations, solid Fe speciation, and bulk sediment N isotope compositions ($\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$), along with previously published sedimentary bulk OC isotopic ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$) and marine palynological data^{13,30}, to identify and differentiate the key processes of OC production, degradation and preservation. To discriminate between OC of marine, terrestrial, and petrogenic origin, we applied an OC mixing model based on the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ and radiocarbon content ($\Delta^{14}\text{C}$) of the bulk OC from a subset of the sediment core samples.

Results and discussion

Changing organic carbon sources related to sea-level changes and glacial dynamics

The Early Holocene in the Northern Hemisphere was marked by a period of profound climate variations, not least a rapid warming of ~3.5 °C^{10,31–33}. Coastal erosion driven by sea-level rise during this Early Holocene warming has frequently been documented as a significant trigger for remobilization of old dormant OC from high-latitude Arctic and subarctic permafrost^{8,34–36}. Likewise, remobilization of dormant terrestrial or petrogenic OC beneath the Greenland ice sheet should be expected during the Early Holocene temperature rise. This hypothesis is confirmed by the old bulk OC pre-depositional ages (i.e., calculated from the offset between analyzed sediment bulk OC age and the corresponding foraminiferal-based modeled age for the same depth level; see “Methods”) of ~0.7 ka observed during the ~12–9.5 cal. ka BP interval in core SA13-ST3-20G (Fig. 3a and Supplementary Table 1). This can be ascribed to a relatively high contribution of old terrestrial-sourced OC that comprises 30–40% of the bulk OC (Fig. 4b), possibly due to the contemporaneous high rates of Greenland ice loss^{37,38}, though post-depositional oxidative degradation of fresh and young OC may also have occurred³⁹. The bulk OC pre-depositional age of ~0.7 ka is, however, much less than that reported in other Arctic environments, e.g., the Siberian-Arctic continental margin (~14 ka³⁴), the Beaufort Sea continental slope (~22 ka⁸) and the eastern Baffin Bay (~4 ka⁴⁰). This discrepancy probably reflects that at our study site the sedimentary OC accumulated between ~12 and 9.5 cal. ka BP contains a relatively small amount of ancient (^{14}C inert) OC, and includes a comparatively high

amount of young, marine-derived OC from local primary productivity that dilutes pre-aged terrestrial-sourced OC.

Although there is not a marked change in the apportioned fraction of marine versus terrestrial OC at ~9.5 cal. ka BP (Fig. 4b), there is an abrupt shift in the bulk OC pre-depositional ages towards much younger values (Fig. 3a). This most likely reflects the addition of freshly-produced marine OC to the bulk OC. This assumption is supported by the contemporaneously high primary productivity (Fig. 5a, b and Supplementary Information). From ~9.5 to 4.2 cal. ka BP, the bulk OC pre-depositional age gradually increases (Fig. 3a), but this observation coincides with a gradual decrease in the fraction of terrestrial OC relative to marine OC (Fig. 4b) and decreasing $\text{C}_{\text{org}}/\text{N}$ ratios (Fig. 3b; see details in the Supplementary Information). The decreasing contribution of terrestrial OC to the bulk sedimentary OC pool rules out the role of aged terrigenous OC reservoirs in causing the observed ageing trend of the latter. Therefore, the gradual ageing of the bulk OC during this time interval is likely related to the accumulation of old marine OC. Bulk OC ageing can also result from marine OC reworking in response to cross-shelf downslope lateral transport under lowering sea level^{41–44}. In fact, a local, gradual lowering of sea level on the southwest Greenland shelf since the Early Holocene has been reported^{45,46} (Fig. 3c). Hence, re-working of marine OC by lateral transport along the southwest Greenland shelf could explain the bulk OC ageing trend between ~9.5 and 4.2 cal. ka BP.

Throughout the Late Holocene (~4.2–0 cal. ka BP), which includes prominent Neoglacial advances from ~2.5 to 0.1 cal. ka BP (Fig. 2a), marine and terrestrial OC contribute ~80% and 18% of the bulk OC, respectively (Fig. 4b), and the pre-depositional age of the bulk OC is relatively constant at ~0.35 ka (Fig. 3a). This observation implies that, during the Late Holocene, input of pre-aged marine OC from cross-shelf transport remained relatively invariant, although the Greenland glaciers have advanced conspicuously since ~2.5 cal. ka BP. It is thus reasonable to assume that Greenland glacier advances did not remobilize old, dormant OC buried underneath the Greenland ice sheet⁴⁷. The continuously high fraction of marine OC since ~2.5 cal. ka BP (Fig. 4b) under the overall lower primary productivity and somewhat higher export productivity conditions (Fig. 5a–d) was likely partially sustained by the progressively increasing influx of FeO_x (Fig. 2b), given a recent finding that FeO_x preferentially binds or adsorbs marine OC³⁹. On the other hand, this high fraction of marine OC since ~2.5 cal. ka BP may also reflect persistently a low influx of terrestrial OC (Fig. 4b) under the prominent Neoglacial advance conditions, leading to a reduced dilution of the marine OC (Fig. 4b). Nevertheless, high burial rates of marine OC since ~2.5 cal. ka BP were primarily controlled by the high SAR (see below).

Multiple variables controlled enhanced Neoglacial organic matter preservation

The $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ of bulk sediment has been widely used as a tracer of N biogeochemical cycling in response to primary and export productivity^{48–50}. Yet, $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ can be altered by several secondary processes, including allochthonous inorganic N addition, differential supply of marine and terrestrial OC sources, and microbial degradation of labile organic matter (OM)^{48,51}. In core SA13-ST3-20G, $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ values do not show correlative trends with dinocyst-reconstructed summer primary productivity (SPP) (Fig. 5a, e), primary productivity geochemical proxies (Ca/Al, CaCO_3 accumulation rates and Si/Al; Fig. 5b, c), or export productivity (Ba/Al; Fig. 5d) (see details in the Supplementary Information). These observations imply that the primary $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ signals were likely not preserved due to overprinting by one or more secondary processes.

Nitrogen in sediments is primarily present in organic- and clay-bound forms, with the latter mainly as ammonium (NH_4^+). The presence of a large fraction of inorganic N can significantly influence bulk $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values⁵². In this study, a positive correlation between TOC and TN_{bulk} ($R^2 = 0.99$) with a near-zero intercept (Supplementary Fig. 1a) implies that almost all the N in the sediment samples was derived from OM⁵³. In core SA13-ST3-20G, the increasing marine OC fraction from ~9.5 to 4.2 cal. ka BP (Fig. 4b) corresponds to a slightly decreasing $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ trend (Fig. 5e) which is typically

Fig. 1 | Map of the northeast Labrador Sea region. Red star and dot in the northeast Labrador Sea denote the position of the studied sediment core SA13-ST3-20G and a nearby sediment core GeoB19905-1, respectively. The green open square denotes the Kobbefjord area in which sediments from three proglacial threshold lakes (Lake IS21, Badesø, and Langesø) were used to reconstruct southwest Greenland glacial²⁸. EGC East Greenland Current, WGC West Greenland Current, IC Irminger Current.

interpreted to reflect an increasing terrigenous OM input^{54,55}. We therefore infer that variations of the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ do not reflect changes in OM sources, and instead propose that the change in sediment $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ was related to the degree of OM degradation, either in the water column or in the sediment. To constrain the proposed causal link, $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ were invoked, considering that greater degradation of marine sediment OM is generally accompanied by higher $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ and lower $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ of the residual OM^{52,56–58}. However, under different redox (i.e., oxic and anoxic) conditions, differential N and C isotope fractionations resulting from OM degradation^{52,59,60} may obscure the original isotopic signals. This is particularly true for N isotope fractionations. For instance, OM degradation under anoxic conditions is typically accompanied by a limited N isotope fractionation relative to what occurs under oxic conditions^{59,60}. We, therefore, choose not to assess the degree of OC degradation using the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ or $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ values for samples deposited during the clearly oxic sedimentary period of ~12–9.5 cal. ka BP, as identified by the trace-element redox proxies (U/Al) (Fig. 5g; Supplementary Information). From ~9.5 to 0 cal. ka BP, a negative correlation between $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ ($R^2 = 0.59$, P value $\ll 0.01$; Fig. 6a) implies that their variations were primarily controlled by the extent of OM degradation.

Enhanced sedimentary OM preservation can be facilitated by multiple factors such as high SAR, fine sediment grain size, anaerobic conditions, and the abundance of FeO_x ^{14–16,61–65}. High SAR can reduce oxygen exposure time and limit OC degradation⁶⁵, while fine-grain sediment and FeO_x have a high adsorption capacity for OC and, thus, can protect OC from degradation^{14–16}. In this study, the accumulation of OC under clearly oxidizing conditions at the sediment–water interface from ~12 to 9.5 cal. ka BP (Fig. 5g) likely reflected a simultaneous increase in OM degradation and FeO_x abundance. In other words, enhanced OM preservation by adsorption to FeO_x was largely counteracted by sustained oxidative OM degradation. For the samples from the ~9.5 to 0 cal. ka BP interval, $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ does not correlate with redox proxies (U/Al) (Supplementary Fig. 1b), but displays negative correlations with SAR ($R^2 = 0.34$, P value $\ll 0.01$; Fig. 6b) and FeO_x abundance

Fig. 2 | Southwest Greenland glacial activity and associated detrital inflow recorded in the sediment core SA13-ST3-20G over the past ~12 ka (Holocene). **a** Principal component analysis PCA1 score indicative of ice fluctuations reconstructed from three proglacial threshold lakes (Lake IS21, Badesø, and Langesø) in southwest Greenland²⁸. Curves above dashed lines indicate glacier advances. **b–d** Sediment reactive iron (oxyhydr)oxide (FeO_x), titanium (Ti), and iron (Fe) concentrations. **e** Average grain size (geometric mean)³⁰. Three separate vertical blue bars denote prominent Neoglacial advance intervals from ~2.5 to 1.7 cal. ka BP, ~1.3 to 1.0 cal. ka BP, and ~0.7 to 0.1 cal. ka BP (the Little Ice Age), respectively²⁹.

($R^2 = 0.48$, P value $\ll 0.01$; Fig. 6c) and a positive correlation with geometric mean grain size ($R^2 = 0.37$, P value $\ll 0.01$; Supplementary Fig. 1c). The correlations suggest that OM preservation was jointly enhanced by reduced oxygen exposure time due to high SAR, the binding/adsorption of OC onto more abundant FeO_x and finer detrital grains. Therefore, the higher $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ values (mean = +6.6‰) from ~9.5 to 2.5 cal. ka BP (Fig. 5e) that correspond to lower SAR (Fig. 3e) and FeO_x abundance and coarser grains (Fig. 2b, e) are likely indicative of relatively stronger OM degradation. In contrast, the subsequently decreasing $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ values to +3.8‰ during the prominent Neoglacial advance (~2.5–0.1 cal. ka BP) interval (Fig. 5e) that correspond to high SAR (Fig. 3e), increasing abundances of FeO_x and decreasing geometric mean grain size (Fig. 2b, e) likely reflect limited sedimentary OM degradation. These relationships imply that high SAR as well as high abundances of FeO_x and fine grains plays a crucial role on OM preservation in the deep troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf.

Glacial advances led to high sediment accumulation rates and high reactive iron (oxyhydr)oxide concentrations

Glacial activity and the associated bedrock erosion can influence detrital clastic sediment transport from continents to coastal environments. Hence, enhanced glacial erosion should be accompanied by a greater delivery of Ti, a common detrital indicator, to the seafloor^{66–70}. Enhanced glacial erosion, however, can result from both advancing or retreating glaciers^{71–73}. According to the results of our analyses of core SA13-ST3-20G, the retreat and advance of the southwest Greenland glacier within the Mid-Holocene and Late Holocene, respectively, feature low and high concentrations of Ti as well as Fe, another detrital indicator³⁰ (Fig. 2a, c, d). These results imply that, in southwestern Greenland, glacier advances were accompanied by stronger glacial erosion relative to glacier retreat. Therefore, the higher Ti and Fe concentrations observed upon entering the prominent Neoglacial advances

Fig. 3 | Organic geochemical and sedimentological data from sediment core SA13-ST3-20G over the past ~12 ka (Holocene). **a** Pre-depositional age of bulk organic carbon (OC) (ka). Error bars denote standard deviations. **b** Molar organic carbon:bulk nitrogen ratio (C_{org}/N). **c** Relative sea-level reconstruction based on shoreline elevations at Sisimiut (Southwest Greenland⁴⁵) and Nanortalik (South Greenland⁴⁶). **d** Total organic carbon concentration (TOC). **e** Sediment accumulation rate (SAR). **f** OC burial rate represented by organic carbon accumulation rate (OCAR). **g** OC burial rate of sediment core GeoB19905-1¹³. **h** Marine OC burial rates of sediment core SA13-ST3-20G.

(~2.5–0.1 cal. ka BP) were controlled by a greater delivery of detrital material arising from stronger glacial erosion. This is further confirmed by results of a recent study that reports high Ti and Fe abundances in another nearby Holocene sediment core (GeoB19905-1, recovered from a trough of the southwest Greenland shelf; Fig. 1) during glacier advances²⁶. Although the strong glacial erosion was marked by higher SAR during the prominent Neoglacial advances (~2.5–0.1 cal. ka BP) (Fig. 3e), which should promote the delivery of Ti and Fe to the sediment, the trends of both Ti and Fe concentrations mirror the geometric mean grain size (Fig. 2c–e) and their concentrations show negative correlations with the geometric mean grain size (Supplementary Fig. 2; $R^2 = 0.46$ and 0.61 , respectively). These observations thus imply that both Ti and Fe concentrations were likely related to detrital input.

Whereas clearly oxidizing conditions prevailed at the sediment–water interface between ~12 and 9.5 cal. ka BP, as indicated by the low U/Al values, reducing conditions predominated for the rest of the time recorded by core SA13-ST3-20G (Fig. 5g). The origin of FeO_x from ~12 to 9.5 cal. ka BP could not be constrained due to the possible addition of FeO_x from detrital Fe-sulfide oxidation after deposition. After ~9.5 cal. ka BP but prior to the Little Ice Age (LIA: ~0.7–0.1 cal. ka BP), the FeO_x content varies concomitantly with total Ti and Fe concentrations (Fig. 2b–d; Supplementary Fig. 3). They are all relatively low from ~9.5 to 2.5 cal. ka BP in response to an overall continuous glacier retreat in southwest Greenland, but followed by a clear increase from ~2.5 and 0.7 cal. ka BP in response to enhanced glacial erosion during the prominent Neoglacial advances (Fig. 2a). In contrast, when entering the LIA, since ~0.7 cal. ka BP, these variables display an opposite trend with increasing FeO_x and decreasing Ti and Fe concentrations

Fig. 4 | Dual isotope mixing model and organic carbon (OC) source apportionments. **a** End members of terrestrial, marine, and petrogenic OC. **b** Modeled OC fractions from different sources. Error bars denote standard deviations.

(Fig. 2b–d). An important authigenic contribution to this FeO_x is unlikely as more reducing conditions apparently predominated during this interval (Fig. 5g). Instead, the FeO_x may have increased as a consequence of a protracted glacial weathering process that extended the oxygen exposure time of detrital Fe-sulfides under weaker glacial erosion conditions, as supported by the lowered Ti and Fe concentrations (Fig. 2c, d). This weakened erosion was possibly caused by a shift to cold-based glaciers⁷⁴, as also seen closer to the ice sheet in the nearby Ameralik Fjord during the LIA⁷⁵. The proposed prolonged exposure time of Fe-sulfides to oxidizing conditions is in part supported by the observed sharp decrease in the pyrite-hosted Fe concentrations during the LIA from ~0.7 to 0.1 cal. ka BP (Supplementary Fig. 4). Nevertheless, except for the oxic interval between ~12 and 9.5 cal. ka BP, these observations imply that the FeO_x in core SA13-ST3-20G is primarily derived from detrital sediments, with a minimal authigenic contribution.

Organic carbon burial rates were variably controlled by productivity and glacial sediment delivery

Processes that control the burial rate of OC from the water column to the seafloor are complex and involve OC production, scavenging, gravitational settling, advective transport, preservation, and degradation. From ~12 to 9.5 cal. ka BP, the relatively invariant bulk and marine OC burial rates were controlled by the consistently low TOC values (~0.3 wt.%) even under high SAR (~870 $g\ m^{-2}\ a^{-1}$) (Fig. 3d–f, h). The low TOC record corresponds to a period of low but increasing primary (Fig. 5a, b) and export productivity (Fig. 5d), and a clearly oxidizing sedimentary environment (Fig. 5g). These observations suggest that the increasing OC production and export that would be expected to increase sediment TOC were largely counteracted by high degradation rates under oxic conditions. The low TOC may also result from dilution by lithogenic mineral components under the high SAR (Fig. 3e).

From ~9.5 to 2.5 cal. ka BP, the bulk and marine OC burial rate increased, while the SAR remained relatively low (~370 $g\ m^{-2}\ a^{-1}$)

Fig. 5 | Geochemical characteristics of sediment core SA13-ST3-20G over the past ~12 ka (Holocene). **a** Summer primary productivity (SPP) (the amount of OC ($\text{g m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) produced during the summer season) reconstructed by the modern analog technique using dinoflagellate cyst (dinocyst) assemblages³⁰. SPP trend is based on its five-point moving average. **b**, **c** Primary productivity proxies: calcium:aluminum ratio (Ca/Al), carbonate (CaCO_3) accumulation rate and silicon:aluminum ratio (Si/Al). **d** Export productivity proxy: barium:aluminum ratio (Ba/Al). **e** Bulk nitrogen isotope composition ($\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$). **f** Organic carbon isotope composition ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$). **g** Sediment–water interface redox condition proxy: uranium:aluminum ratio (U/Al). The gray horizontal bar in (**g**) represent oxic depositional conditions.

(Fig. 3e, f, h). The bulk and marine OC burial rates during this interval were primarily determined by the relatively high TOC (~1.6 wt.%) (Fig. 3d) as a result of persistently high primary productivity (Fig. 5a, b), though OM was not well preserved as indicated by the high $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ values (~+6.7‰) (Fig. 5e). During the prominent Neoglacial advances at ~2.5 cal. ka BP, but prior to the LIA, the bulk and marine OC burial rates displayed a rapid increase (Fig. 3f, h). During the LIA, an interval that was accompanied by further expanding Greenland glaciers²⁹, bulk OC burial rates decreased slightly (Fig. 3f). Nevertheless, changes in the bulk and marine OC burial rates since ~2.5 cal. ka BP follow a similar trend to the SAR as well as the detrital flux indicators Ti and Fe, but are less strongly correlated to TOC (Fig. 2c, d and 3d–f, h). This implies that the burial rates of sedimentary bulk and marine OC were strongly modulated by Greenland glacial erosion-driven SAR during the prominent Neoglacial advances from ~2.5 to 0.1 cal. ka BP. Thus, the SAR plays a first-order role on bulk and marine OC burial, though FeO_x and fine grains partly contribute to the preservation of OC (Fig. 6c and Supplementary Fig. 1c; see above).

Neoglacial organic carbon burial in the deep troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf is globally important

To expand our understanding of OC burial rates at a regional scale, we attempted to compare our results with those derived from the study of other nearby Holocene sediment cores from the deep troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf. Apart from core SA13-ST3-20G in this study, OC burial rate data from only one core GeoB19905-1 (Fig. 1) are available¹³. The two sediment cores exhibit comparable OC burial rate patterns throughout the Holocene, with a similar increasing trend reaching high average values of 13.9 ± 1.0 and $23.1 \pm 4.4 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$, respectively, since ~1.3 cal. ka BP (Fig. 3f, g). Assuming that these two records are broadly representative of OC burial rates of the deeper troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf,

Fig. 6 | Cross-plots of geochemical data for samples from ~9.5 to 0 cal. ka BP. **a** $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ versus $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$. **b** $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ versus SAR. **c** $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ versus FeO_x . $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{bulk}}$ values for samples from ~12 to 9.5 cal. ka BP were excluded in the three cross-plots since these samples were deposited under different redox conditions compared to the ones deposited under anoxic conditions from ~9.5 to 0 cal. ka BP (see details in the text). In particular, the endpoint at the age of 9.5 cal. ka BP showing an anomalous value of SAR was not included in (**b**). **a–c** The area bracketed by dashed lines illustrates the 95% confidence band of the best fit represented by a solid line.

we assign a mean OC burial rate value of $\sim 18.5 \pm 5.7 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$ for the two sediment cores. Sediment deposition is mostly limited to the deeper troughs and basins of the shelf ($> \sim 300 \text{ m}$ water depth) and we infer the area of sediment accumulation based on a previous estimate of the area of pure mud deposition of $\sim 0.025 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$ using the western Greenland sea-bed mapping by Gougeon et al.²⁴ Based on this area we estimate, the OC burial rate since $\sim 1.3 \text{ cal. ka BP}$ is $\sim 0.46 \pm 0.14 \times 10^{12} \text{ g a}^{-1}$, of which the buried marine OC component is $\sim 0.37 \pm 0.11 \times 10^{12} \text{ g a}^{-1}$. Although the deep troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf account for only $\sim 0.005\%$ of the global ocean surface area^{6,76}, the estimated annual OC burial is equivalent to $\sim 0.27 \pm 0.08\%$ of the total global OC burial per year in marine sediments ($\sim 169 \times 10^{12} \text{ g}^6$). Notably, the estimated mean areal OC burial rate in the deep troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf is similar to that of many high-latitude fjords, including from eastern and western Canada, Svalbard, Antarctica, northwestern Europe, Chile, and New Zealand (Supplementary Fig. 5 and Supplementary Table 2).

It has been estimated that the Labrador Sea takes up $\sim 39 \times 10^{12} \text{ g CO}_2$ annually from the modern atmosphere through deep convection and, thus, is a significant sink for atmospheric CO_2 ⁷⁷. Our estimated annual OC burial of $\sim 0.46 \pm 0.14 \times 10^{12} \text{ g C}$ in the deep troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf since $\sim 1.3 \text{ cal. ka BP}$ is equivalent to $\sim 1.69 \pm 0.51 \times 10^{12} \text{ g CO}_2$, or $\sim 5\%$ of the present-day annual CO_2 sequestration by the Labrador Sea deep convection⁷⁷. Hence, it is an important but currently unrecognized component of the total ocean carbon sink in the Labrador Sea. It would be valuable to explore whether other shelf areas near recently advancing glaciers and ice sheets also demonstrate this high level of carbon burial.

Conclusions

To understand how OC burial is modulated by Holocene glacial activity, we carried out a suite of geochemical analyses on sediment samples from core (SA13-ST3-20G) recovered from a deep basin of the southwest Greenland shelf, in the northeast Labrador Sea. We did not observe an increase in OC burial rates related to glacier retreat, but found that prominent Greenland glacier advances during the Neoglacial cooling ($\sim 2.5\text{--}0.1 \text{ cal. ka BP}$) were synchronous with an obvious increase in marine-rich OC burial rates which were promoted by elevated SAR sustained by enhanced glacial erosion. Based on the mean of the OC burial rates ($\sim 18.5 \pm 5.7 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$) derived from the analysis of the only two sediment cores recovered from the deep troughs and basins of the shelf, we estimated an annual OC burial of $\sim 0.46 \pm 0.14 \times 10^{12} \text{ g}$ in the deep troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf since the middle of the prominent Neoglacial advances at $\sim 1.3 \text{ cal. ka BP}$. Given the large uncertainty on this spatial extrapolation, additional studies of sediment OC burial in the deep troughs and basins of the shelf would be required to better constrain this estimate. In addition, high-resolution analyses of recent and centennial-scale OC burial rates in the deep troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf would not only improve the accuracy of estimates of current OC burial rates but likely better reveal the nature of processes responsible for these high OC burial rates. Finally, to elucidate the role of FeO_x on the preservation of marine OC, a determination of the concentration and isotope composition of the Fe-associated OC in these sediments would be helpful^{15,39}.

Our study also highlights that, during discrete cold time intervals, OC burial in the deep troughs and basins of the southwest Greenland shelf may supplement the oceanic, physical carbon sink provided by Labrador Sea deep-water convection. This emphasizes the importance of the climatically sensitive Labrador Sea region in regulating global carbon cycling and climate feedback.

Methods

Core location, sampling, and treatment

A marine sediment gravity core (SA13-ST3-20G; $64^\circ 26.7425' \text{N}$, $52^\circ 47.6486' \text{W}$, water depth 498 m , core length 587 cm) was recovered from a deep basin of the southwest Greenland shelf (Fig. 1) north off the Godthåbsfjord (Nuup Kangerlua) complex in August 2013 during a cruise of the Greenlandic research vessel *Sanna*. A total of 60 samples were collected

from the sediment core SA13-ST3-20G at a $\sim 10 \text{ cm}$ resolution. The stable carbon isotope composition of the sedimentary organic matter ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$) was determined on decarbonated (24-h fuming in a desiccator in the presence of an open beaker of concentrated HCl (36%)) aliquots of freeze-dried sediment samples, and was analyzed using an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Micromass-IsoprimeTM) coupled to an Elementar Vario Micro-Cube elemental analyzer operated in a continuous flow mode at Geotop-UQAM, Canada. The age-depth model for the core was established based on 32 Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (AMS) ^{14}C dates of mixed benthic foraminifera and mollusc shells using the age-depth modeling software OxCal v4.3.2⁷⁸. A detailed description of these analyses can be found in ref. 30.

Grain-size analyses

Grain-size analyses were carried out at a 5-cm resolution in the Department of Geoscience, Aarhus University, on a Sympatic HELOS laser diffractometer, equipped with a Quixel wet disperser, a 6 mm cuvette, and R4 and R7 lenses. Before analyses, samples were shaken in a solution of 1.5% $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ peptizer and demineralized water in an end-over-end shaker for 3 days to ensure dispersal. The samples were then wet-sieved to separate fine ($d < 63 \mu\text{m}$) and coarse ($d > 63 \mu\text{m}$) fractions. The coarse fraction was analyzed using the R7 lens and the fine fraction using the R4 lens. Each sample was measured three times to obtain a median value. For each sample, 36 grain-size intervals were measured. The average grain size (geometric mean) was calculated using the following equation $\mu = \sum^n P_i S_i$ where S_i is the size class, P_i is the percentage of size S_i , and n is the total number of size classes⁷⁹.

Bulk carbon data analyses

The total carbon (TC) and organic carbon (TOC) concentrations of the core sediment samples ($n = 60$) were determined at the Geotop-UQAM Stable Isotope Laboratory following the protocol developed by Hélie et al.⁸⁰. Briefly, for the analyses of TC and TOC, freeze-dried and grounded samples were first weighed ($\sim 9 \text{ mg}$) in tin and silver capsules, respectively. Samples in the silver capsules were acid fume-treated with concentrated HCl (36%) for 24 h in a desiccator to remove the carbonate fraction, and then wrapped in tin capsules. TC and TOC concentrations were measured using an elemental analyzer (Carlo Erba NC2500), and reported as a weight percent (wt.%) of the bulk sample. The standard deviations ($\pm 1\sigma$) for the TC and TOC analyses were better than 0.1%, based on replicate measurements of organic standard substances. Carbonate contents of the core sediments was calculated using the following equation: $(\text{CaCO}_3 = (\text{TC} - \text{TOC}) \times 8.333)$.

Major- and trace-element concentrations

For major- and trace-element concentration analyses, a $\sim 20 \text{ mg}$ aliquot of the freeze-dried subset ($n = 19$) of the bulk samples was digested in a mixture of concentrated HF (2 mL) and HNO_3 (1 mL) and heated on a hot plate at 95°C for 48 h. The digested samples were then dried and reacted with a 20% H_2O_2 solution until all organic matter was removed. The rest of the samples were first ashed between 400 and 1000°C by continuous ramped heating for a total 4.5 h in a muffle furnace at McGill University to remove organic matter. These ashed samples were then acid-digested as described above for the subset of samples. Following the acid digestions, the solutions were evaporated to dryness, and the residues were reacted with 2 mL of 6 M HCl at 100°C for 24 h to dissolve fluorides. After final evaporation of samples from both digestion procedures, all samples were taken up in 1 mL of a 2% HNO_3 solution and gravimetrically diluted with 2% HNO_3 to a final dilution factor of, respectively, ~ 500 and ~ 1500 for major and trace-element analyses. The diluted samples were analyzed for major element concentrations by iCAP 6000 inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) and for trace-element concentrations by Fisher iCAP-Q inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) in the Geochemical Analysis Laboratory at the McGill University. Major and trace-element concentrations are reported in wt.% and $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, respectively.

To verify that the two different digestion methods yielded similar analytical results, two of the studied samples (samples 10 and 46) were

treated using both digestion protocols. They yielded very comparable results, within 0.1% standard deviation of the mean for the major elements Ti, Ba, Fe, and Ca. International reference standard materials MESS-4 and PACS-3⁸¹ were used for major- and trace-element calibration and processed through the ashing procedure. The analytical accuracy, estimated from the relative standard deviation of the mean, was generally better than 10% for the major (Al, Ti, Fe, Ba, Ca) and trace (U) elements.

Solid iron speciation

Solid Fe speciation was carried out according to the method described by Poulton and Canfield⁸². Sequential extraction of operationally-defined carbonate-bound, (oxyhydr)oxides-bound and magnetite-bound Fe was conducted on ~100 mg of ground, freeze-dried sediment samples ($n = 32$). First, Fe associated with carbonate minerals, such as ankerite, siderite, or ferrous dolomite, was extracted by reacting samples with ~10 mL of a 1 M buffered (pH ~4.5) sodium acetate-acetic acid solution. The mixture was allowed to react for 48 hours at 50°C on a shaking table. Second, Fe bound to (oxyhydr)oxides (FeO_x), such as goethite, hematite, lepidocrocite, were extracted from the residues with ~10 mL of a 50 g/L sodium dithionite solution buffered with 0.35 M acetic acid and 0.2 M sodium citrate to a pH of 4.8. This reaction was allowed to proceed for 2 hours on a shaking table at room temperature. Third, Fe associated with mixed-valence phases, such as magnetite, was extracted with ~10 mL of a 0.2 M ammonium oxalate-0.17 M oxalic acid solution that was buffered with ammonium hydroxide to a pH of 3.2. The reaction was carried out on a shaking table at room temperature for 6 h. After each of these extractions, leachates were separated by pipetting after centrifugation at 3900×*g* for 5 min, diluted tenfold with 2% HNO₃ and analyzed using a Thermo Scientific iCAP 6000 series ICP-OES in the Geochemical Analysis Laboratory at the McGill University. Finally, the amount of Fe associated with pyrite was determined gravimetrically (assuming a FeS₂ stoichiometry) by trapping chromium-reducible sulfides that were liberated from a CrCl₂ reduction⁸². In this study, an international marine sediment standard, PACS-3, was analyzed to monitor the analytical reproducibility of each extracted Fe speciation phase. The analytical reproducibility was better than 5%.

Nitrogen concentration and its isotope composition

The bulk N concentrations and its isotope composition in sediment core SA13-ST3-20G samples ($n = 60$) were analyzed using an Eurovector elemental analyzer (EuroEA3028-HT) coupled to an Isoprime 100 continuous flow isotope ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS) at Concordia University (Montreal, Canada). The concentrations and isotope compositions were obtained from the same calibrations. A 5-level calibration curve was constructed daily using an in-house β-alanine standard ($N = 15.7\%$, $\delta^{15}N = -2.21 \pm 0.24\%$) ($n = 3$ or 4)⁸³ and an internationally certified USGS25 standard ($\delta^{15}N = -30.4\% \pm 0.27\%$) ($n = 1$)⁸⁴, with signal intensities spanning the entire range of the instrument. Samples were run in duplicate or triplicate, together with the β-alanine and USGS25 standards that were inserted between each set of six samples. The standard deviation on N concentration determinations, based on duplicate or triplicate analyses of the same samples, was <0.1 wt.%. The N isotope compositions are reported using the delta (δ) notation in per mil relative to the standard of atmospheric N (Air-N₂), using the formula $\delta^{15}N = ((^{15}N/^{14}N)_{\text{sample}} / (^{15}N/^{14}N)_{\text{Air-N}_2} - 1) \times 1000$. The standard deviation of δ¹⁵N values, based on duplicate or triplicate sample measurements, was generally better than 0.3‰, and the relative standard deviations of the mean between the analyzed β-alanine ($-2.24 \pm 0.20\%$, $n = 21$) and USGS25 ($-29.34 \pm 0.49\%$, $n = 23$) were better than 0.25‰.

Radiocarbon analyses

Radiocarbon analyses of the bulk OC for a subset ($n = 18$) of sediment core SA13-ST3-20G samples were carried out by accelerator mass spectrometry (AMS) MICADAS (Mini Carbon Dating System) at the University of Ottawa (Canada). The sample pre-treatment protocol, processing and

definitions of media codes can be found in refs. 85, 86. Data were processed using the BATS data reduction software, as described in ref. 87. The fraction modern carbon, F¹⁴C, was calculated as the ratio of the sample ¹⁴C/¹²C to the standard ¹⁴C/¹²C (Ox-II) measured in the same data block. Both ¹⁴C/¹²C ratios were background-corrected, and the result was corrected for fractionation (both instrumental and procedural fractionations) using the online AMS measured ¹⁴C/¹²C ratio and was normalized to δ¹³C (PDB). Radiocarbon ages are calculated as $-8033 \ln(F^{14}C)$ and reported in ¹⁴C years BP (BP = AD 1950), as described in Stuiver and Polach⁸⁸. Errors on ¹⁴C ages (1σ) are based on counting statistics as well as ¹⁴C/¹²C and ¹³C/¹²C variations between data blocks. A calibration was performed using OxCal v4.2.4⁸⁹ with the IntCal20 calibration curve⁸⁹.

As we compare the bulk OC age and co-occurring sediment depositional ages from the high-resolution foraminiferal-based age model presented in ref. 30, the radiocarbon dates of the bulk OC were re-calibrated using the calibration curve Marine 13 and a marine reservoir correction value, ΔR, of 140 ± 35 years. These corrections were also applied to generate an age-depth model for the same sediment core SA13-ST3-20G³⁰. Although the value of ΔR may change due to varying supplies of terrestrial OC, the core site is well connected to the open ocean, which minimizes the impact of a changing ΔR on the results of this study^{90,91}. Age offsets (ka) were then calculated between the bulk OC and the corresponding age-depth model age for the sediment. The offset values provide an estimate of bulk OC ages prior to its deposition at the sediment surface.

Organic carbon source apportionment

Given that petrogenic OC from Cretaceous sedimentary rocks has been shown to be an important OC source to West Greenland shelf seas⁴⁰, this study considers a potential petrogenic OC contribution from ancient sedimentary rocks, in addition to autochthonous and/or allochthonous marine and terrigenous OC. Thus, a three-endmember mixing model, based on a Markov Chain Monte Carlo Bayesian approach⁹², using stable carbon isotope (δ¹³C_{org}) and radiocarbon content (Δ¹⁴C) as tracers was employed to apportion the fractional contributions of marine, terrestrial and petrogenic OC (f_{marine} , $f_{\text{terrestrial}}$, $f_{\text{petrogenic}}$, respectively) (Supplementary Information) from the bulk OC pool, assuming mass-balance:

$$\Delta^{14}C_{\text{initial}} = f_{\text{marine}} \times \Delta^{14}C_{\text{marine}} + f_{\text{terrestrial}} \times \Delta^{14}C_{\text{terrestrial}} + f_{\text{petrogenic}} \times \Delta^{14}C_{\text{petrogenic}} \quad (1)$$

$$\delta^{13}C_{\text{bulk}} = f_{\text{marine}} \times \delta^{13}C_{\text{marine}} + f_{\text{terrestrial}} \times \delta^{13}C_{\text{terrestrial}} + f_{\text{petrogenic}} \times \delta^{13}C_{\text{petrogenic}} \quad (2)$$

$$1 = f_{\text{marine}} + f_{\text{terrestrial}} + f_{\text{petrogenic}} \quad (3)$$

The δ¹³C_{bulk} is the measured value, and Δ¹⁴C_{initial} refers to the fraction modern carbon before deposition. To account for radiocarbon decay after deposition, the Δ¹⁴C_{initial} of core SA13-ST3-20G was calculated using the following equation^{8,93}:

$$\Delta^{14}C_{\text{initial}} = (F^{14}C \times e^{\lambda t} - 1) \times 1000\% \quad (4)$$

where F¹⁴C is the measured fraction of modern carbon. λ is the decay constant of radiocarbon, and *t* is the time since deposition, according to the core chronology.

The statistical source apportionment relies on knowledge of the isotopic source profiles of the three end members. Here, we employed the reported δ¹³C and Δ¹⁴C values for topsoil and subsoil of northeastern Greenland as the terrestrial OC end member, i.e., δ¹³C_{ter} = $-26.5 \pm 1.35\%$ and Δ¹⁴C_{ter} = $-354.6 \pm 258.6\%$ ⁹⁴, considering the lack of relevant records in southwest Greenland. The marine OC end member is based on literature values for high-latitude marine phytoplankton (δ¹³C_{mar} = $-21.0 \pm 2.6\%$; Δ¹⁴C_{mar} = $-50 \pm 12\%$)⁹⁴. For the petrogenic OC end member, the δ¹³C_{org} value of the East Greenland Permian–Triassic strata was adopted

($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{petr}} = -28.86 \pm 4.09\text{‰}$) due to the unavailable ancient sedimentary $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ records in the southwest Greenland⁹⁵, and the $\Delta^{14}\text{C}$ ($\Delta^{14}\text{C}_{\text{petr}}$) is assumed to be -1000‰ .

Organic carbon burial rate determination

OC burial rate is derived from the OC accumulation rate (OCAR) and was calculated using the following equations⁹⁶:

$$\text{SAR} = \text{LSR} * \text{DBD} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{OCAR} = \text{SAR} * \text{TOC} / 100 \quad (6)$$

where SAR = sediment accumulation rate ($\text{g m}^{-2} \text{a}^{-1}$), LSR = linear sedimentation rate (m a^{-1}), DBD = dry bulk density (g m^{-3}), TOC = total organic carbon concentration (wt.%). In this study, LSR is calculated based on the age-depth model for core SA13-ST3-20G³⁰; DBD data for the core were estimated using measurements from a nearby sediment core GeoB19905-1 as a function of depositional ages¹³.

Data availability

All data generated and used in this study are provided in the Supplementary Dataset 1 (spreadsheet).

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Author contributions

Y.W. and P.M.J.D. designed this study. E.A. and M.S.S. provided samples. Y.W. performed analyses of major- and trace-elemental concentrations. Y.W. and Y.G. carried out nitrogen concentration and isotope analyses. E.A. performed total carbon and total organic carbon concentration analyses. P.M.J.D., Y.G., and A.M. provided guidance on analytical protocols as well as access to laboratory infrastructures and equipment. Y.W. wrote the manuscript with input from P.M.J.D., M.S.S., A.V., and A.M. All authors were involved in the interpretation of the results and participated in the editing process of the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

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